

CODATA Activities and Achievements

The document that follows provides a quick listing of important CODATA activities for 2020 and then highlights some key achievements of 2019.

CODATA Activities 2020

International FAIR Convergence Symposium convened by CODATA and GO FAIR, 22-23 October 2020, Paris, France

The International FAIR Convergence Symposium will provide a forum for advancing international and cross-domain convergence around FAIR. The event will bring together a global data community with an interest in combining data across domains for a host of research issues - including major global challenges, such as those relating to the Sustainable Development Goals. Outcomes will directly link to the [CODATA Decadal Programme 'Data for the Planet: making data work for cross-domain grand challenges'](#) and to [the developments of GO FAIR community towards the Internet of FAIR data and services](#).

Participation is open to ALL researchers and data experts, particularly those with an interest in participating in the CODATA Decadal Programme and in the GO FAIR Community. There will be a mechanism for participants to organise workshop sessions: for example, GO FAIR INs, CODATA TGs and other groups are encouraged to participate and to organise sessions.

CODATA General Assembly, 24 October 2020, Paris, France

The two-day Symposium will be followed on 24 October by the CODATA General Assembly which will see the election of new Officers, Executive Committee and Task Groups. Documentation for proposing new Task Groups and for extending existing Task Groups, as well as documentation for nominating candidates for the Executive Committee and the Officer roles of Secretary General and Treasurer will be circulated in April. CODATA members, national committee, international scientific unions and Task Groups are encouraged to start considering their proposals and nominations well in advance.

Decadal Programme: Making data work for cross-domain grand challenges

A lot of CODATA activity in 2020 will be directed towards building partnerships and collaboration for the **Decadal Programme** for the International Science Council: **Making data work for cross-domain grand challenges.**

The Decadal Programme features in the [ISC Action Plan as Project 2.1 on 'Data-Driven Interdisciplinarity'](#). A brief summary can be found on the [CODATA website](#) and an overview is given in this [slide deck](#) and in the [presentation recently given to the ISC Committee on Science Planning](#).

Decadal Programme: Preparatory Activities

2020 will see a large number of activities and meetings to build partnerships, collaboration and consensus for the Decadal Programme: making data work for cross-domain grand challenges. At the moment, the following are planned and others may be organised.

- IIASA and CODATA Workshop, 24-25 February, Laxenburg, Austria: Workshop and meetings to discuss FAIR data for systems analysis.
- [Research Data Alliance Plenary, 18-20 March, Melbourne, Australia](#): Birds of a Feather Session on the Decadal Programme.
- CODATA Executive Committee Meetings, 31 March-3 April, Ottawa, Canada.

- [IASSIST Conference, 19-22 May, Gothenburg, Sweden](#): Panel Session organised with DDI Alliance.
- [Sustainability Research and Innovation, 14-17 June, Brisbane, Australia](#): Workshop on the Decadal Programme.
- CASEarth and CODATA Joint Workshop on Big Earth Data, date to be determined, Sanya, China: a detailed workshop to plan collaboration between CASEarth and CODATA around policy and interoperability issues for data relating to SDGs 11 (urban resilience), 13 (climate change, DRR), and 15 (life on earth / biodiversity).
- [Dagstuhl Workshop, DDI 4 Core, 5-9 October, Schloss Dagstuhl, Germany](#): intensive workshop with DDI on Core metadata interoperability.
- [Dagstuhl Workshop, Interoperability of Metadata Standards in Cross-Domain Science III, 12-16 October, Schloss Dagstuhl, Germany](#): the third in our series of workshops developing solutions and recommendations to address cross-domain interoperability.
- [UN World Data Forum, 19-21 October, Bern, Switzerland](#): a panel session has been proposed for this important global event.
- [International FAIR Convergence Symposium convened by CODATA and GO FAIR, 22-23 October, Paris, France](#): a key event to advance cross domain convergence.
- [International Open Data Conference, 18-20 November, Nairobi, Kenya](#): CODATA has been asked to play a leading role in organising sessions and strands relating to FAIR data, Open Science and the Decadal Programme.

CODATA Achievements 2019

Here we give a very brief list of key achievements, structured around our four strategic foci:

1. Promoting **consensus and good practice**
2. Developing **policies** for Open Science and FAIR data
3. Advancing **data science**
4. Building capacity through **data skills and training**

Strategy and Good Practice

The bulk of CODATA activity has been devoted to preparing the **Decadal Programme: making data work for cross-domain grand challenges**. This has involved numerous meetings, workshops and position papers for ISC, which resulted in the inclusion of this activity in the [ISC Science Action Plan](#). The approach and methodology has been further refined through the [second Dagstuhl Workshop on Interoperability of Metadata Standards in Cross-Domain Science](#).

The [message from CODATA President, Barend Mons](#) about the CODATA strategy for the next few years is highly relevant to this initiative.

Data Policy

A major data policy contribution of 2019 was the [Beijing Declaration on Research Data](#) which came out of a policy workshop organised before the CODATA 2019 Beijing Conference and in response to global developments, including the recent Chinese State Council statement on the good management of research data.

A CODATA team led by Paul Uhlir and Hans Pfeiffenberg, and including other members of the Data Policy Committee, has been performing a 20-Year Review of GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility. The review will be published at the end of February 2020.

Data Science

CODATA convened no fewer than four **conferences** in 2019:

- Our major conference [CODATA 2019 Beijing](#) on the theme of [Towards next generation data-driven science: policies, practices and platforms](#).
- Two large workshops on FAIR Research Data Management in Institutions, at [Drexel University, Philadelphia](#) and at the [Finnish National Archives, Helsinki](#).
- A large symposium on [data visualisation in Africa](#), the second of an ongoing series.

Papers from all these events will appear in the [Data Science Journal](#) which has a new [Editor-in-Chief, Mark Parsons](#).

CODATA Task Groups

The latest set of [CODATA Task Groups](#) cover a range of significant topics (including [disasters data](#), [smart cities](#), [mathematical tools for systems analysis](#), [citizen science for the SDGs](#) and [agriculture data](#) and others) and will deliver in 2020. The Task Groups are very active and announcements will be made about their events and outputs for 2020. For example, the Task Group on Linked Open Data for Disaster Risk Research, produces a very well-received [monthly newsletter on Disaster Risk Reduction and Open Data](#).

Fundamental Physical Constants and the SI System

THE DEFINING CONSTANTS OF THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM OF UNITS

Defining constant	Symbol	Numerical value	Unit
hyperfine transition frequency of Cs	$\Delta\nu_{\text{Cs}}$	9 192 631 770	Hz
speed of light in vacuum	c	299 792 458	m s ⁻¹
Planck constant*	h	6.626 070 15 × 10 ⁻³⁴	J Hz ⁻¹
elementary charge*	e	1.602 176 634 × 10 ⁻¹⁹	C
Boltzmann constant*	k	1.380 649 × 10 ⁻²³	J K ⁻¹
Avogadro constant*	N_{A}	6.022 140 76 × 10 ²³	mol ⁻¹
luminous efficacy	K_{cd}	683	lm W ⁻¹

*These numbers are from the CODATA 2017 special adjustment. They were calculated from data available before the 1st of July 2017.

and mole) were redefined according to exact numerical values derived from the Planck constant (h), the elementary electric charge (e), the Boltzmann constant (kB), and the Avogadro constant (NA), respectively. All the SI System base units are now derived from the exact values for Fundamental Physical Constant defined by the CODATA Task Group.

One of the notable achievements of 2019-2020 was the contribution of the [CODATA Task Group on Fundamental Physical Constants](#) to the major redefinition of the SI System of Units. [By a vote taken on 16 November 2018 and effective on 20 May 2019](#), the remaining four base units of the SI System (the kilogram, ampere, kelvin,

2018 CODATA RECOMMENDED VALUES OF THE FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS OF PHYSICS AND CHEMISTRY NIST SP 959 (June 2019)

An extensive constants list is available at physics.nist.gov/constants.

Quantity	Symbol	Numerical value	Unit
¹³³ Cs hyperfine transition frequency	$\Delta\nu_{\text{Cs}}$	9 192 631 770	Hz
*speed of light in vacuum	c	299 792 458	m s ⁻¹
*Planck constant	h	6.626 070 15 × 10 ⁻³⁴	J Hz ⁻¹
*elementary charge	e	1.602 176 634 × 10 ⁻¹⁹	C
*Avogadro constant	N_{A}	6.022 140 76 × 10 ²³	mol ⁻¹
*Boltzmann constant	k	1.380 649 × 10 ⁻²³	J K ⁻¹
*luminous efficacy	K_{cd}	683	lm W ⁻¹
electron volt (e/C) J	eV	1.602 176 634 × 10 ⁻¹⁹	J
Josephson constant 2e/h	K_{J}	483 597.848 4... × 10 ⁹	Hz V ⁻¹
von Klitzing constant 2πh/e ²	R_{K}	25 812.807 45...	Ω
molar gas constant $N_{\text{A}}k$	R	8.314 462 618...	J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Stefan-Boltzmann const. $\pi^2k^4/(60h^3c^2)$	σ	5.670 374 419... × 10 ⁻⁸	W m ⁻² K ⁻⁴

*Defining constants of the International System of Units (SI).

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Quantity	Symbol	Numerical value	Unit
(unified) atomic mass unit $\frac{1}{12}m(^{12}\text{C})$	u	1.660 539 066 60(50) × 10 ⁻²⁷	kg
Newtonian constant of gravitation	G	6.674 30(15) × 10 ⁻¹¹	m ³ kg ⁻¹ s ⁻²
fine-structure constant $e^2/(4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c)$	α	7.297 352 5693(11) × 10 ⁻³	
inverse fine-structure constant	α^{-1}	137.035 999 084(21)	
Rydberg frequency $\alpha^2m_e c^2/(2\hbar)$	cR_{∞}	3.289 841 960 2508(64) × 10 ¹⁵	Hz
vac. magnetic permeability $4\pi\alpha\hbar/(e^2c)$	μ_0	1.256 637 062 12(19) × 10 ⁻⁶	N A ⁻²
vac. electric permittivity $1/(\mu_0 c^2)$	ϵ_0	8.854 187 8128(13) × 10 ⁻¹²	F m ⁻¹
electron mass	m_e	9.109 383 7015(28) × 10 ⁻³¹	kg
proton mass	m_p	1.672 621 923 69(51) × 10 ⁻²⁷	kg
proton-electron mass ratio	m_p/m_e	1836.152 673 43(11)	
reduced Compton wavelength $\hbar/(m_e c)$	λ_{C}	3.861 592 6796(12) × 10 ⁻¹³	m
Bohr radius $\hbar/(\alpha m_e c)$	a_0	5.291 772 109 03(80) × 10 ⁻¹¹	m
Bohr magneton $eh/(2m_e)$	μ_{B}	9.274 010 0783(28) × 10 ⁻²⁴	J T ⁻¹

The number in parentheses is the one-sigma (1σ) uncertainty in the last two digits of the given value.

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Data Skills and Training

The [CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science](#) are a major ongoing success. In 2019 these two week foundational courses were run in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia; Trieste, Italy and San José, Costa Rica. Advanced workshops and a new strand on data stewardship (as part of the [FAIRsFAIR project](#) in which CODATA is a partner) were also run in Trieste in 2019. The first data school of 2020 has already taken place in Pretoria, South Africa. Others are planned for Abuja, Nigeria; Trieste, Italy (August); Canada (October) and São Paulo, Brazil (December). [A new video provides information about the Data Schools and the opportunities for alumni to become helpers, instructors and co-chairs.](#) Three of the initiative's co-chairs - [Marcela Alfaro, Sara El Jadid and Bianca Peterson](#) - are alumni of the data schools!

CODATA and CODATA China also ran a [training workshop on Big Data and Machine Learning](#) in Beijing in September 2019 prior to the CODATA Beijing Conference.

Finally, two other data school alumni - Shaily Gandhi and Felix Enyiam - have been tasked with developing [CODATA Connect](#), an early career and alumni network. Shaily and Felix will shortly be announcing a series of webinars and other activities. **Watch this space!**

